

^{35}Cl Nqr Studies of Trichloroacetic Acid Hydrogen Bonded Complexes

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The nqr spectra of ten trichloroacetic acid complexes with various proton acceptors have been studied. The results obtained together with the literature data enabled to analyse more precisely the influence of the acid-base properties on the resonance frequencies of chlorine atoms. The shape of the $\nu_{\text{NQR}}(\Delta pK_a)$ curve can be reconstructed in terms of the inductive effect caused by a continuous change of the dipole moment located within the hydrogen bridge. An analogy with the dipole moment behaviour in solutions, where the proton-transfer equilibrium has been detected, does exist.

THERE are already several data related to nqr spectra of trichloroacetic acid (TCA) with both nitrogen and oxygen bases¹⁻⁵. Pietrzak *et al.*⁴ and Nogaj⁶ correlated, similarly to the procedure used for the description of the hydrogen bond polarity⁷, the average shift of the nqr frequency, $\Delta\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}}$, with ΔpK_a (equal to $pK_a(\text{BH}^+) - pK_a(\text{AH})$). On the other hand, the increase of hydrogen bond polarity in the solution can be related to the contribution of the polar proton transfer state. The analysis presented by Nogaj and Pietrzak *et al.* showed that the TCA complexes behave, as compared with other hydrogen bonded systems⁸, in particular manner, namely they are characterised by a flat shape of the $\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}}(\Delta pK_a)$ plot expressed by a small value of the ξ parameter in equation (1).

The aim of the present contribution was to yield new data on the nqr behaviour of TCA complexes and to perform a numerical analysis of all the results gathered so far.

Experimental

Solid complexes were prepared by crystallisation from equimolar TCA-base solutions in acetonitrile. The complex composition was tested by chlorine analysis. Measurements of the resonance frequencies were performed at liquid-nitrogen temperature (77 K) on a ISSh-1-13M pulse spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

The results of measurements in the form of all observed signals and calculated average (weighed) $\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}}$ values are presented in Table 1. These data, together with those already published and treated in the unified manner, enabled to find the correlation

between $\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}}$ and ΔpK_a in terms of the proton transfer model. According to this model, in the hydrogen bonding there exists the equilibrium

Therefore, the average resonance frequency can be expressed as a linear function of the contribution of the proton transfer (PT) state

$$\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}} = \bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}} X_{\text{HB}} + \bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}} X_{\text{PT}} \quad (1)$$

where, HB and PT indices correspond to non-proton-transfer (HB) and PT states. $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}}$ and $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$ denote the average frequencies of those states. The equilibrium constant of the PT reaction $K_{\text{PT}} = X_{\text{PT}}/X_{\text{HB}}$ can be, on the other hand, combined with ΔpK_a acc. to equation^{10,11}

$$\log K_{\text{PT}} = \xi \Delta pK_a + \delta \quad (2)$$

where, ξ and δ are constants characteristic for the given series of complexes. In Fig. 1, there are taken into account all results reported till now for which the pK_a values are known. The correlation plot was computed by fitting, using the least-squares method, with relations (1) and (2). The values of $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}}$, $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$ and ξ parameters equal to 40.0 MHz, 38.1 MHz and 0.17, respectively. ΔpK_a at which 50% PT form is realised equals to -0.5.

The results obtained in this paper allow to draw the following conclusions.

(i) The scattering of experimental points with respect to the plot of the best fitting is much greater than that suggested previously^{4,6}. Therefore, the TCA complexes can not be distinguished, from this point of view, among other hydrogen bonded systems. This confirms the observations made so far⁹ that the nqr frequencies are also strongly affected by the local fields resulting from the presence of polar groups in neighbouring molecules.

TABLE I—³⁵Cl Nqr Frequencies in TCA Complexes

Amine	$\bar{\nu}_{NQR}$ MHz	Number of resonance lines	$\bar{\nu}$ MHz	pK_a^{**} amine
2-Bromopyridine	98.458, 98.722, 99.084, 99.117, 99.481, 99.639	6	99.07	0.71
Diphenylamine	98.221, 98.300, 98.835	3	98.45	0.79
3-Cyanopyridine	98.111, 98.973, 99.023	3	98.70	1.35
4-Cyanopyridine	98.648*, 99.426	2	98.91	1.86
Benzo[h]quinoline	97.806, 98.325, 99.098	3	98.41	3.88
Quinoline	97.997, 98.774, 98.804	3	98.52	4.93
Morpholine	98.007, 98.154, 98.488, 98.585	4	98.31	8.49
Tributylamine	97.493, 97.977, 98.075, 98.107, 98.188, 98.459	6	98.05	9.93
Pentylamine	97.952, 98.206, 98.393, 98.493, 98.598*, 98.754, 98.911, 99.331	8	98.58	10.63
Dibutylamine	97.695, 97.767, 97.894, 98.004, 98.362, 98.428, 98.497, 98.550, 98.770, 98.838	10	98.28	11.25

* Doublet. ** Ref. 9.

Fig. 1. ³⁵Cl average nqr frequencies plotted against ΔpK_a : (1) acetonitrile^{1,13}, (2) *o*-methylbenzoic acid^{2,9}, (3) benzoic acid^{3,9}, (4) acetone^{3,9}, (5) *m*-methylbenzoic acid^{3,9}, (6) benzaldehyde^{3,9}, (7) phenol^{3,9}, (8) ethyl acetate^{3,9}, (9) cyclohexane^{1,9}, (10) acetophenone^{3,9}, (11) 4-methoxybenzaldehyde^{3,9}, (12) *t*-butanol^{3,9}, (13) *N,N*-dimethylformamide^{1,13}, (14) acetamide^{1,9}, (15) 2-pyrrolidone^{1,13}, (16) *N,N*-dimethylacetamide^{1,9}, (17) ϵ -caprolactam^{1,13}, (18) 2,6-dimethyl 4-pyrone^{3,9}, (19) 2-bromopyridine, (20) pyridine *N*-oxide^{3,9}, (21) diphenylamine, (22) 4-methylpyridine *N*-oxide^{3,9}, (23) 3-cyanopyridine, (24) 4-cyanopyridine, (25) 3-bromopyridine^{3,9}, (26) benzo[h]quinoline, (27) quinoline, (28) pyridine^{3,9}, (29) 4-methylquinoline^{3,9}, (30) 4-methylpyridine^{3,9}, (31) 2,6-dimethylpyridine^{3,9}, (32) 2,4-dimethylpyridine^{3,9}, (33) 2,4,6-trimethylpyridine^{3,9}, (34) morpholine, (35) tributylamine, (36) pentylamine, (37) triethylamine^{1,9}, (38) dibutylamine; (a) TCA^{4,14}, (b) value averaged over the frequencies for potassium³, ammonium³, rubidium³ and thallium³ bis-trichloroacetates, (c) TCA-caesium salt³, (d) TCA-sodium salt³. The first upper index relates to nqr frequency and the second one to ΔpK_a value; (C) oxygen bases, (□) nitrogen bases.

The conditions for each particular complex can be completely different.

(ii) No essential differences in the behaviour of nitrogen and oxygen bases have been detected. The

average deviation of experimental points from the best fitted curve is the same for both types of proton acceptors. It means that the pK_a values are in this case a good measure for the description of proton donor-acceptor properties.

(iii) The values of $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}}$, $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$, ξ and δ parameters are close to those reported by Nogaj for 16 complexes, however, the ξ parameter appeared to be distinctly higher. It means that the shape of $\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}}$ (ΔpK_a) plot in the inversion range (close to the ΔpK_a value at which $K_{\text{PT}}=1$) is considerably steeper. The results of nqr studies are in a good agreement with the conclusions drawn from the dipole moment investigation on hydrogen bonded complexes of carboxylic acids with amines in benzene solutions¹⁶.

In Fig. 1, we confronted the extrapolated $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}}$ and $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$ values with those for TCA dimers (a) and its ionic state in caesium (c) and sodium (d) salts. Besides the value for hydrogen bis-trichloroacetates (average for various cations) is marked (b). The confrontation shows that $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}}$ value is very close to that for pure TCA which exists, in the solid state, in the form of hydrogen bonded dimers. Generally no agreement is observed between $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$ and ν for ionic states in various salts. Except caesium salt the nqr frequencies are considerably higher than $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$ showing some covalent character of TCA-cations interactions. Certainly geometric factors play also some role in a creation of electric field gradient around the quadrupole Cl nuclei. The $\bar{\nu}_{\text{NQR}}$ value for hydrogen bis-trichloroacetate(b) had to be expected in the middle between $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}}$ and $\bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$. In fact, it is markedly shifted in the direction of non-polar hydrogen bonded form. The reason might be the same as for ionic PT form.

The frequency increment $\Delta\nu = \bar{\nu}_{\text{HB}} - \bar{\nu}_{\text{PT}}$ can be related to an enhancement of dipole moment $\Delta\mu_{\text{PT}}$ caused by the proton transfer process. The magnitude of $\Delta\mu_{\text{PT}}$ has been estimated¹⁶ from direct dipole moment measurements in solution as equal to $22 \cdot 10^{-30}$ C-m. By assuming purely electrostatic inductive mechanism of the interaction

between the hydrogen bonding moment and quadrupole nuclei one gets similar value depending on the accepted $\partial\nu/\partial E_z$ value, which is reported¹⁷ in the limits 0.42-0.68 MHz m/GV.

References

1. O. KH. POLESCHCHUK, YU. K. MAKSYUTIN, O. F. SYCHEV, K. K. KOSHELEV and I. G. ORLOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1976, 6, 1431.
2. D. BIRDENKAPP and A. WEISS, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 788.
3. H. CHICHARA and N. NAKAMURA, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, 37, 156.
4. J. PIETRZAK, B. NOGAJ, Z. DRGA-SZAFRAN and M. SZAFRAN, *Acta Phys. Polon.*, A, 1977, 52, 779.
5. H. CHICHARA and N. NAKAMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, 44, 1980.
6. B. NOGAJ in "Progress in Applications of Resonance Techniques in Chemistry", ed. L. SOBCZYK, PWN, Warsaw, 1984.
7. L. SOBCZYK, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1979, 51, 1659.
8. E. GRECH, J. KALENIK and L. SOBCZYK, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1979, 1567; 1983, 2005; 1985, 311.
9. D. D. FERRIN, "Dissociation Constants of Organic Bases in Aqueous Solution", Butterworths, London, 1965; Supplement, 1972.
10. P. HUYSKENS and Th. ZREGGERS-HUYSKENS, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1964, 61, 81.
11. H. RATAJCZAK and L. SOBCZYK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, 50, 556.
12. E. M. ARNETT, E. J. MITCHELL and T. S. S. R. MURTY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1974, 96, 3875.
13. R. HUISGEN, H. BRADÉ, H. WALZ and I. GLOGGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 1487.
14. G. KORTÜM, W. VOGEL and K. ANDRUSSOW, "Dissociation Constants of Organic Acids in Aqueous Solution", Butterworths, London, 1961.
15. A. A. BOGUSLAVSKII and S. K. SHCHERBAKOVA, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser. Fiz.*, 1978, 42, 2135.
16. L. SOBCZYK and Z. PAWEŁKA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1974, 832.
17. J. KALENIK, Thesis, University of Wrocław, 1981.